

Antibacterial Effects of Yoghurt on Selected Diarrhoeagenic Bacteria

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Abstract

Bacterial diarrhoea is still a serious infection in most developing countries including Nigeria. Despite the seriousness however, especially in children, the use of antibiotics is discouraged by medical practitioners. Therefore, it becomes imperative to search for alternative methods of treatment. Yoghurt is a fermented food drink known to offer a lot of health benefits. It is therefore worthwhile to investigate whether it has antibacterial potential against common diarrhoeagenic bacteria. This study therefore was carried out to investigate the antibacterial effects of selected yoghurt samples on common diarrhoeagenic bacteria viz: *Salmonella typhi*, *Shigella dysenteriae* and *Escherichia coli* using agar well diffusion assay. Ten different brands of commercially prepared yoghurt samples were evaluated in this study. The presence of lactic acid bacteria (LAB) in the yoghurt samples was determined using standard microbiological assays. The growth inhibition mediated by most of the yoghurt samples was superior to the one mediated by some of the antibiotics used as control. The growth inhibition ranged from 10.75 ± 3.06 mm to 19.00 ± 0.00 mm on *Salmonella typhi*, 9.75 ± 1.56 mm to 15.00 ± 0.00 mm on *Shigella dysenteriae* and 11.45 ± 0.90 mm to 16.25 ± 0.56 mm on *Escherichia coli*. The LABs isolated from the yoghurt samples were *Lactobacillus bulgaricus*, *L. fermentum*, *L. casei* and *Streptococcus lactis* and the LAB counts ranged from 3.3×10^2 to 1.3×10^3 CFU/mL. It is therefore conceivable that yoghurts can be exploited in treating bacterial diarrhoea instead of antibiotics that can cause antibiotic induced diarrhoea during therapy thereby aggravating the medical condition.

Keywords: Diarrhoeagenic bacteria, antibiogram, yoghurt, growth inhibition, non-conventional therapy

INTRODUCTION

Diarrhoea remains one of the major causes of death in children in many developing and underdeveloped countries. Although the illness in most cases is self-limiting, however when diarrhoea is as a result of bacterial infections such as *Escherichia coli*, *Shigella* spp., *Salmonella* spp., *Campylobacter* spp. etc, antibiotic therapy may be required. However, because of the increase in the development of antibiotic resistance by many bacterial species and that the administration of antibiotics can lead to the development of antibiotic induced diarrhoea, the search for more effective therapy is imperative.

Different types of non-conventional therapies are often employed by people living in rural areas for the treatment of gastrointestinal diseases including diarrhoea. Examples of such is the use of raw 'ogi' (Aderiye and Laleye, 2003; Adebolu *et al.*, 2007). The low pH, bacteriocin, diacetyl etc produced by the *Lactobacillus plantarum* present in 'ogi' according to Adebolu *et al.* (2012) accounts for its growth inhibitory activity against common diarrhoeagenic bacteria. Fermented milk

products such as cheese whey and butter milk are also used for treating many ailments in folk medicine. These products are known to possess a lot of microorganisms including lactic acid bacteria (LAB) and bio-metabolites that are reported to have growth inhibitory activities on common diarrhoeagenic bacteria (Olorunfemi *et al.*, 2007; Adebolu and Awe, 2014, Adetunji and Adebolu, 2017). Other examples of fermented milk products are yoghurt, kefir and sour cream. Yoghurt, which is a semisolid fermented milk product that is rich in LAB, is often consumed for its probiotic properties (Adolfsson *et al.*, 2004). The aim of this study was to evaluate the antibacterial activity of commercially prepared yoghurts on common diarrhoeagenic bacteria in the bid of searching for non-conventional therapies for the management of diarrhoeal cases.

METHODOLOGY

Ten different samples of yoghurts were bought from different stores in Akure town. The yoghurt samples used were Farm pride, Cedaar, LIZ, Hollandia, Denice, Habib, Dolait, MM, Superyogo and Fresh Blueboat. Clinical samples of *Salmonella typhi*, *Shigella dysenteriae* and *Escherichia coli* collected from the Microbiology Laboratory of State Specialist Hospital, Akure (now FUTA Teaching Hospital, Akure) were used as test bacteria. Total bacterial count in the yoghurt samples was carried out by pour plate technique as described by Kawo *et al.* (2006) while isolation and identification of microorganisms present in yoghurt samples were done according to Holt *et al.* (1994). Antibiotic susceptibility test of the collected bacterial isolates and the growth inhibitory effect of the yoghurt samples on the isolated test bacteria were carried out using standard agar diffusion techniques. Data were expressed in percentages and as means of values \pm SD as the case may be.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The total bacterial counts of the yoghurt samples worked on revealed that Fresh Blueboat yoghurt had the highest bacterial count of 1.9×10^3 CFU/mL while Hollandia yoghurt had the least count at 2.3×10^2 CFU/mL. De-nice yoghurt had the highest coliform count of 5.0×10^2 CFU/mL while MM yoghurt had the least at 2.0×10^2 CFU/mL. No faecal coliform count however was recorded in all the yoghurt samples. Dolait had the highest LAB count of 1.33×10^3 CFU/mL while Farm Pride, Cedaar and LIZ yoghurts had the least count of 3.3×10^2 CFU/mL each (Table 1). The total bacterial counts detected in the yoghurt samples however are within limits because the standard aerobic bacterial counts in yoghurts should not exceed 10^7 CFU/mL according to CODEX Alimentarius (2003). The observation that faecal coliforms like *E. coli* are completely absent is a good one. This is an indication that the producers of the evaluated yoghurt samples employed Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP) (Igbabul *et al.*, 2014). The following bacterial species were isolated from the different yoghurt samples: *Lactobacillus bulgaricus*, *L. fermentum*, *L. casei*, *Streptococcus thermophilus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Serratia marcescens*, *Bacillus cereus* and *B. subtilis*. Four out these bacterial species, *Lactobacillus bulgaricus*, *L. fermentum*, *L. casei* and *Streptococcus thermophilus* are LABs. Three out of the four types of LAB isolated; *Lactobacillus bulgaricus*, *L. fermentum* and *Streptococcus thermophilus* were found in Hollandia yoghurt while 1-2 types of the isolated LABs were identified in the other yoghurt samples except Fresh Blueboat yoghurt in which no LAB was isolated (Table 2). Farm Pride yoghurt exerted the highest growth inhibition of *S. typhi* (19.0 ± 0.00 mm) while De-nice had the least effect of 10.75 ± 3.06 mm. Superyogo yoghurt on the other hand exerted the highest growth inhibitory effect on *Sh. dysenteriae* (15.0 ± 0.00 mm) while MM yoghurt had the least effect of 9.75 ± 1.56 mm. Superyogo yoghurt also exerted the highest growth inhibitory effect on *E. coli* (16.25 ± 0.56 mm) while LIZ yoghurt had the least effect at 11.45 ± 0.00 mm (Table 3). Fresh Blueboat yoghurt on

the other hand, did not inhibit the growth of any of the test bacteria. The antibacterial activity displayed by the yoghurt samples on the test bacteria in this study agrees with the report of Ayeni *et al.* (2019) and Wiktorczyk-Kapischke *et al.* (2024) in which the yoghurt samples they worked on exerted growth inhibition of the test bacteria although they did not specify the types of yoghurts they carried their studies on. The observed growth inhibition exerted by the yoghurt samples examined in this study could however be attributed to the presence of LABs in the yoghurts. Four different types of LABs comprising *Lactobacillus bulgaricus*, *L. fermentum*, *L. casei* and *Streptococcus thermophilus* were isolated from the yoghurt samples evaluated. Earlier works had shown that LAB produce metabolites that are inhibitory to the growth of many pathogenic bacteria (Cherrington *et al.*, 1991; Abd El-Gawad *et al.*, 2014).

Table 1: Total Viable Microbial Counts of the Yoghurt Samples

Samples	Total Bacterial Count (CFU/ml)	Total coliform Count (CFU/ml)	Total Faecal coliform Count (CFU/ml)	Total LAB Count (CFU/ml)
Farm Pride	1.47 x 10 ³	2.8 x 10 ²	0.0	3.3 x 10 ²
Cedar	9.7 x 10 ²	0.0	0.0	3.3 x 10 ²
LIZ	3.7 x 10 ²	0.0	0.0	3.3 x 10 ²
Hollandia	2.3 x 10 ²	3.0 x 10 ²	0.0	8.3 x 10 ²
De-nice	7.7 x 10 ²	5.0 x 10 ²	0.0	3.7 x 10 ²
Habib	2.7 x 10 ²	0.0	0.0	1.07 x 10 ³
Dolait	4.3 x 10 ²	0.0	0.0	1.33 x 10 ³
MM	1.53 x 10 ³	2.0 x 10 ²	0.0	3.3 x 10 ²
SuperYogo	1.67 x 10 ³	0.0	0.0	1.13 x 10 ³
Fresh blueboat	1.9 x 10 ³	0.0	0.0	0.0

Table 2: Types and frequency of occurrence of bacterial species isolated from selected yoghurt samples

Bacterial species	Yoghurt samples										P(%)
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	
<i>L. bulgaricus</i>	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	+	-	40
<i>L. fermentum</i>	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	40
<i>L. casei</i>	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	30
<i>Strep. thermophilus</i>	-	+	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	40
<i>S. epidermidis</i>	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	40
<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	30
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	30
<i>B. substilis</i>	-	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	70

Total types/LAB 3/2 5/2 2/2. 5/3 3/1 2/1 3/2 3/1 4/1 2/0

Key: A-Farm Pride, B-Cedaar, C- LIZ, D-Hollandia, E-De-nice, F-Habib, G-Dolait, H-MM, I-Superyogo, J-Fresh Blueboat, P-Percentage occurrence

Table 3: Growth inhibitory effect of yoghurt samples on common Diarrhoeagenic Bacteria

Treatment	Diameter of zones of inhibition		
	<i>Salmonella typhi</i> (mm)	<i>Shigella dysenteriae</i> (mm)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> (mm)
Habib	16.00±3.00	13.00±2.00	15.15±0.15
Dolait	15.50±2.50	13.75±1.25	13.50±3.50
Superyogo	15.50±1.00	15.00±0.00	16.25±0.56
Hollandia	12.25±0.25	10.95±0.05	11.85±0.15
Denice	10.75±3.06	12.50±2.50	12.10±2.10
Farm Pride	19.00±0.00	11.65±0.18	13.05±1.55
MM	13.00±1.00	9.75± 1.56	15.00±1.00
Blueboat	0.00±0.00	0.50±0.00	1.00 ±0.00
LIZ	14.8± 0.00	10.6 ± 0.00	12.4 ± 0.00
Cedaar	12.55±2.95	13.45±2.55	11.75±3.75
CIP	16.17±1.70	16.49±6.09	14.84±4.12
CHL	8.67±3.67	9.67±4.67	4.83±3.84
AUG	13.17±1.70	12.50±4.50	14.50±4.50
STR	15.42±1.09	14.92±2.59	0.00±0.00

Mean zone diameter (n=2) ± SD

Key: CIP = Ciprofloxacin (30ug); CHL = Chloramphenicol (30ug); AUG= Augmentin (30ug); STR = Streptomycin (ug)

CONCLUSION

This study revealed that all the yoghurt samples evaluated except Blue boat brand exerted growth inhibition of the test diarrhoeagenic bacteria worked on. The inhibition mediated by most of the yoghurt samples was comparable to that of most of the antibiotics evaluated and, in some cases, superior. Therefore, yoghurts can be exploited in treating bacterial diarrhoea instead of antibiotics which can induce diarrhoea during antibiotic therapy.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Since this present work is just an *in vitro* assay demonstrating the antibacterial activity of yoghurts on common diarrhoeagenic bacteria, more research works are recommended to investigate whether the administration of yoghurt will actually exert therapeutic effect in cases of diarrhoea and also to know the types of yoghurts that can be exploited.

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